

QUIZ**LAST NAME: HERRERA****FIRST NAME: SHEANNA MARIE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MS Word 2016

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **In doing qualitative research involving the participation of human subjects, what elements should a researcher consider?**

- Informed consent, human subject research protection, and confidentiality.**¹
- Informed consent and confidentiality.
- Human subject research protection only.
- Confidentiality and human subject research protection.

2. **Citation is required when including a source in writing a paper. Select the situation below that may require citation.**

- Exact words from a source are to be quoted.

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 76.

- Idea, data, or method associated with specific source are to be used.
- All of the above are correct.**²
- None of the above.
3. **Standard British English and Standard American English have fundamental differences in pronunciation, spelling, and so on. Given the SAE in the next sentence, substitute it with SBE: “The Philippines has increasing rate of HIV infection. Ms. Herrera aims to identify the effectiveness of the availability of over-the-counter HIV home test kit in the course of early diagnosis of HIV in the Philippines. The study will commence on June 14, 2020.” Tick the correct answer.**
- ‘The Philippines have an increasing rate of HIV infection. Ms Herrera aims to identify the effectiveness of the availability of over-the-counter HIV home test kit on the course of early diagnosis of HIV on the Philippines. The study will commence on 14 June 2020’.**³
- ‘The Philippines have an increasing rate of HIV infection. Ms. Herrera aims to identify the effectiveness of the availability of over-the-counter HIV home test kit in the course of early diagnosis of HIV in the Philippines. The study will commence on June 14, 2020.’
- Both choices are correct.
- No SBE can be applied.
4. **The WHO style guide uses non-discriminatory language. Following the said house style, how would you refer to people aged 65 years old and above?**

²Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, 8th edition., Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86.

³ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press: EUCLID University, 2015), 54–55, accessed August 31, 2019, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

- Geriatric
- Older people
- Elderly
- B & C are correct.**⁴

5. **A qualitative research design should designate the philosophical paradigm based on the nature of reality, knowledge, or value. The research design of Ms. Herrera is stated as, “the assessment of the awareness of college students in urban areas (using open-ended interview) on the health effects of e-cigarettes.” What philosophical paradigm does it describe? Tick the correct answer.**

- Ontology.
- Axiology.**⁵
- Epistemology.
- All of the above are correct.

6. **According to Turabian guidelines, which of the following is true with regards to quotations?**

⁴WHO, *WHO Style Guide* (20 Avenue Appia, 1211 Geneva 27, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2004), 58.

⁵ Philip Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*, 2016, accessed September 25, 2019, https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=2&v=KRHvxY3N708.

- Italicizing word is allowable if you want to emphasize words from the original passage. Rules that indicate changes will apply.**⁶
- Modification of quotation is not allowed even if it contains a typographic error. Modifying will be taken for legal action by the author.
- Deleting a colon in the original passage is not allowed in quotations. Instead, permissible change will be modifying colon into a semicolon.
- All of the above are correct.
7. **Following the WHO style guide, how would you quote a foreign language? Tick the best answer.**
- Quoting a foreign language requires English translation. The end of the quotation should say, “(translation from [original language, translator, author, date]).”
- Quoting a foreign language should retain the original words no matter the length. Modification will be taken for legal action by the author.
- Quoting a foreign language requires English translation on selected words that the author would like to emphasize to the readers. The rest should be left in the original language.
- Quoting a foreign language requires English translation. The end of the quotation should say, “(translation from [original language]).”**⁷
8. **Choose from the following the correct Turabian reference template given the following details:**

Author: Kate L. Turabian

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 211.

⁷WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, 24.

Editors: Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams

Year published: 2013

Edition number: 8

Book title: *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers.*

Publisher's name: University of Chicago Press.

Place of publication: Chicago

- Turabian, Kate L., ed. Booth, Wayne C., Colomb, Gregory G., and Williams, Joseph M. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers.* 8th edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Kate L. Turabian, 2013. "A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers." Edited by Gregory G. Colomb, Wayne C. Booth, and Joseph M. Williams. 8th edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Turabian, Kate L., 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers.* 8th edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams.
- Turabian, Kate L. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers.* Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. 8th edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.⁸**

9. **When writing chemical names following WHO house style, what naming rule should a writer follow?**

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 129.

- International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC).⁹**
- International Council of Chemical Association.
- The Royal Society of Chemistry.
- International Chemistry Associations.

10. **What are the typical elements of an abstract? Tick the correct answer.**

- Figures and tables from methodology and literature review.
- Summary of the research problem and key findings.¹⁰**
- Full details of recommendations and theories behind.
- All of the above are correct.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adu, Philip. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*, 2016. Accessed September 25, 2019. https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=2&v=KRHvxY3N708.

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008.

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press: EUCLID University, 2015. Accessed August 31, 2019. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. 8th edition. Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

⁹ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, 6.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 168.

WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. 20 Avenue Appia, 1211 Geneva 27, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.